

APOLLO3[®]-Based Solutions to OECD / NEA TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Benchmark Exercise 1

Ulysse Dubuet^{1,*}, Barbara Vezzoni¹, Antonio Galia¹, Roland Lenain¹, Raphaël Hirsch¹, Elliott Kuhn¹, Hamza Azakaye¹

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Etudes des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, Gif-sur-Yvette, 91191, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803500

ABSTRACT

As part of CEA activities on lattice calculation scheme development and codes verification and validation, this paper presents the simulation strategy and results obtained with APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR for OECD/NEA WB1 Benchmark Exercise 1. The sensitivity of the full-core simulation to some lattice calculation parameters is evaluated. Good agreement with the benchmark measurements and reference calculations is obtained.

Keywords: Lattice calculation scheme, APOLLO3[®], Benchmark, Watts Bar Unit 1, V&V

1. INTRODUCTION

For several years, the *Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives* (CEA) has been developing a new-generation neutronics codes: the deterministic APOLLO3[®] [1] and the stochastic TRIPOLI-5 [2]. These codes are suitable for modeling different reactors types spanning from large scale PWRs up to existing designs or novel concepts (e.g., LW-SMRs, AMR or Gen-IV concepts). Each concept has its specialties that need to be taken into account by dedicated calculation schemes, i.e. a set of options for each physics involved chosen on the basis of a specific Verification, Validation and Uncertainties Quantification strategy (V&V&UQ) [3, 4].

To ensure the robustness of the codes and schemes implemented, as well as their prediction capabilities, CEA has joined international benchmarks on the V&V strategy, taking advantage of comparisons with experimental data, when available, or to other modeling tools and options. The OECD/NEA Watts Bar Unit 1 (TVA-WB1) benchmark [5] is one of these international benchmark allowing to test several aspects of the neutronics simulation tools and multi-physics couplings, with zero-power tests to multi-cycle depletion.

This paper presents the results for the Hot Zero-Power tests using the deterministic code APOLLO3[®] [1] via the SIGAR API [6], developed at CEA for simplifying and standardizing the study of PWRs. It has been the occasion to test several modeling options, in particular for the lattice part, and to compare them to the reference results [7] and to CEA results submitted to the benchmark [8].

The reactor specifications are briefly presented in Section 2. The simulation codes and strategies adopted are presented in Section 3. The results for the Hot Zero-Power test are presented in Section 4. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section 5.

*Corresponding author: ulyse.dubuet@cea.fr

2. WATTS BAR UNIT 1 BENCHMARK

The “OECD/NEA TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Multi-Physics Multi-Cycle Depletion” benchmark [5] is based on real plant data of the first three cycles of the Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA) Watts Bar Nuclear Unit 1 (WB1). This work focus on the Hot Zero Power (HZP) case (exercises 1), within the first loading cycle.

The WB1 reactor is a typical Westinghouse 4-loop reactor of 3411 MWth at 15.511 MPa. 193 assemblies (of 21.5 cm pitch) of 17x17 pins are loaded with UO₂ fuel. Each assembly contains 1 instrumentation tube, 24 guide tubes and the remaining 264 fuel pins. Three different ²³⁵U enrichment are used in the first cycle: 2.1%, 2.6% and 3.1%. The fuel stacks measure 365 cm. In the first loading cycle, the core reactivity is controlled by burnable poison (Pyrex) pins, boron and control rods made of stacks of Silver-Indium-Cadmium (AIC) and boron carbide (B₄C). The control rods (RCCAs) are divided into 8 banks (4 operation banks: A, B, C, D; and 4 safety banks: SA, SB, SC and SD), that can be inserted up to 230 steps.

Eight spacer grids maintain the pins in each assembly: the top and bottom grids are made of Inconel-718 while the other six are made of Zircaloy-4. The top Inconel grid is above the active region, and is considered part of the top reflector.

More detailed description of the reactor core are available in the benchmark specifications [5].

The first exercise focuses on the HZP start-up tests. Several conditions are investigated: boron concentrations of 1170, 1230, 1285, and 1291 ppm; moderator temperatures of 560, 565 and 570 K; and various rod insertion configurations. The core instrumentation has not been modeled in detail.

3. SIMULATION TOOLS

In Section 3.1, we briefly present the simulation tools used to model the HZP tests. Then, in Section 3.2, we present the different modeling options adopted for the different test cases studied.

3.1. Codes used

APOLLO3[®] [1] has been used via the SIGAR API [6].

APOLLO3[®] [1] is the new multi-purpose deterministic code in development since 2007 by CEA with the strong support of EDF and Framatome. A rationalization approach aiming to unify tools dedicated to calculating the different reactor types (PWRs, VVER, RNR, etc.) is at the basis of its development. It allows both lattice and core calculations for all kind of geometries.

SIGAR [6] is a Python package developed at CEA to easily setup PWR configurations. It facilitates the use of APOLLO3[®] routines and benefits from a simple interface containing historic methods used in the two-step calculation scheme. SIGAR is still under development and the application to TVA-WB1 has allowed to test several features from the lattice calculations to the core simulation for a complete static configuration.

3.2. Lattice, Reflector & Core Modeling

Several lattice modeling options have been used to generate the homogenized cross-sections (Multi-Parameter Outputs, MPOs). The complete list of parameters and chosen values is given in Table I.

3.2.1. Lattice calculations

Two-dimensional lattice calculations of the TVA-WB1 assemblies have been performed using the TDT-MOC transport solver with transport corrected-P0 (P0c), P1 and P3 scattering anisotropies. Two dis-

cretization methods are used: the method of characteristics (MOC) with an asymptotic synthetic acceleration DP1 (STEP), and the MOC with linear surface and DP1 acceleration (linear). The 281 energy groups CEAV512 libraries (based on JEFF3.1.1) are used as input nuclear data and the multicell solver with the Livolant-Jeanpierre (L-J) formalism [9] is used to compute the $P_{i,j}$ for self-shielding calculations.

To generate a database of homogenized cross-sections for core simulations, lattice calculations have been performed with a homogeneous B1 leakage model [10]. The cross-sections are homogenized on a two- or four-group energy mesh, and pin-by-pin (PBP) and full-assembly (FA) spatial meshes using SPH equivalence with flux-volume normalization. For each assembly, one set of cross-sections is generated with each of the spacer grid materials diluted in the moderator, and one set of cross-sections is generated with no grid material, enabling the explicit modeling of the grids at the core level.

Table I. List of parameters.

Options	Values
Nuclear Data library	CEAv5.1.2 (JEFF3.1.1)
Anistropy	P0c, P1 & P3
Energy groups	2 & 4
Spatial homogenizations	Pin-by-Pin (PBP) & Full Assembly (FA)
Lattice calculation scheme	Direct 281gr
Reflector models	$P_{i,j}$ Multi-cell, Formalism L-J, TDT-MOC (Step/Linear)
Number of radial reflector traverses	1D
Reflector anisotropy	1 & 4
Equivalence	P0c, P1 & P3
Core solver options	SPH Flux-Volume MINOS (Diffusion)

3.2.2. Reflector calculations

Reflector cross-sections used in core simulations have been obtained from 1D slab calculations combined with albedo equivalence. 2 axial slabs (for the top and bottom reflectors) and 5 radial slabs (an averaged radial slab, and 4 at 0°, 28.3°, 40.2° and 45° from the lattice axes, see Figure 1) have been simulated. The averaged radial slab is obtained after core cylindrization and conserving the neutron pad mass in a 7-cm diluted pseudo-neutron pad. Its geometry is given in Figure 2. The fissile material used in the 1D calculations is obtained by full homogenization of representative assemblies: no burnable absorbers and a 3.1% fuel enrichment.

The lattice calculations have been performed using the IDT solver [1] with P0c, P1 and P3 scattering anisotropies.

3.2.3. Full-core calculations

Full-core simulations have been performed for all the combinations of MPO parameters. The core has been meshed into 101 axial cells: the spacer grids are axially divided into 3 cells, the space in-between into 10 cells of approximately 5 cm each and the axial reflectors into 5 cells. An additional axial division is added at the bottom of the inserted control rods, if necessary. The results have then been processed to match the benchmark mesh requirements.

The solver used is the MINOS solver [1, 11], using the diffusion approximation.

Figure 1. Radial traverses selection, on WB1 loading map (taken from [5]).

Figure 2. Averaged radial traverse geometry.

4. THE HZP START-UP TESTS

The simulation results are then compared to the benchmark's reference calculation with KENO-VI, using the ENDF/B-VII.0 library [7], and to TRIPOLI-5 results [8]. Due to the large number of parameter sets (144), only a few of them are compared here for the first exercise of the benchmark. The combination of options studied in this work are detailed in Table II.

Table II. Selected calculation and homogenization parameter sets.

Parameter set	Anis.	# Groups	Spatial Homog.	# Traverses	Refl. Anis.
a	P0c	2	FA	1	P0c
b	P0c	2	PBP	1	P0c
c	P0c	2	PBP	1	P3
d	P3	2	PBP	1	P3
e	P0c	4	PBP	1	P3
f	P0c	2	PBP	4	P3

To assess the performances of modeling options, the reactivity are compared for different rod insertion situations [5]. This allows to evaluate the simulation results with the different absorber present in the core. The reactivity $\Delta\rho$, in pcm, is given by Equation (1), and the results are compared in Table III.

$$\Delta\rho = (k_{\text{eff}} - 1) / k_{\text{eff}} \cdot 10^5 \text{ [pcm]} \quad (1)$$

While full assembly (FA) calculation lead to -610 pcm maximum deviation from criticality, deviations for the pin-by-pin (PBP) are between 120 and 390 pcm, with mean deviations between 200 (for more refined calculation parameters) to 320 pcm. Some limitations arise when inserting absorbers in the core: the introduction of B_4C leads to a 40 pcm decrease of reactivity, for all parameter configurations. This may indicate some limitations either on the nuclear data library used, or on constant parameters between all configurations studied here (e.g., the radial mesh of absorber pins for the lattice calculation). The full insertion of Bank D control rods, i.e., the insertion of both B_4C and AIC, leads to another reactivity decrease of 60 – 80 pcm, depending on the parameter configuration.

The Differential soluble Boron Worth (DBW) is calculated based on two cases with All Rods Out (ARO) at 565 K respectively with boron concentration of 1291 ppm and 1170 ppm. The Isothermal Temperature Coefficient (ITC) is calculated by changing only the moderator temperatures from 560 to 570 K and keeping the boron concentration at 1291 ppm and ARO configuration. The fuel temperature is constant, at 565 K. The results are compared to the measurements and reference calculations [7] in Table IV.

Table III. Computed $\Delta\rho$ (pcm) of critical rod cases for different parameter sets using APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR and from benchmark's reference calculations (KENO-VI). In cases 3 – 10, the indicated banks are fully inserted, and the bank D is also partially inserted.

Param. set	Case Bank	1-D	2-ARO	3-A	4-B	5-C	6-D	7-SA	8-SB	9-SC	10-SD	Mean (std)
	a (FA)		-480.3	-437.9	-602.6	-576.3	-609.7	-586.4	-568.2	-588.4	-532.8	
b		-270.7	-228.5	-389.5	-304.9	-377.4	-349.2	-318.0	-333.1	-294.9	-294.9	-316.1 (46.1)
c		-217.5	-176.3	-306.9	-275.8	-299.9	-282.8	-292.9	-273.7	-244.6	-244.6	-261.5 (38.9)
d		-195.4	-154.2	-289.8	-259.7	-283.8	-268.7	-276.8	-257.7	-227.5	-227.5	-244.1 (40.9)
e		-211.4	-170.3	-316.0	-258.7	-298.9	-285.8	-284.8	-266.7	-241.6	-241.6	-257.6 (41.2)
f		-160.3	-119.1	-223.5	-237.6	-205.4	-219.5	-278.8	-198.4	-197.4	-197.4	-203.7 (40.7)
KENO-VI		-10.1	32.1	-120.4	-64.2	-96.2	-91.7	-99.9	-67.6	-101.8	-102.5	-72.2 (45.5)

Table IV. Computed DBW (pcm/ppm) and ITC (pcm/K) for different parameter sets using APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR and from benchmark's measurement and reference calculations.

	Meas.	KENO-VI	a (FA)	b	c	d	e	f
DBW [pcm/ppm]	-10.77	-10.21	-10.2	-10.3	-10.3	-10.2	-10.2	-10.2
ITC [pcm/K]	-3.91	-5.7	-3.5	-2.8	-3.0	-3.6	-2.8	-3.2

The DBW obtained is close to the reference calculation and does not significantly depend on the lattice parameters. The calculated ITC, on the contrary, vary with the different parameter configuration but a clear trend is not identified. Moreover, it can be noted that there are important uncertainties on the benchmark ITC values, and on its calculation method, especially if the fuel temperature is considered constant (at 565 K) or not.

The different bank worth, in pcm, are calculated by keeping both the moderator and fuel at 565 K and the boron concentration at 1170 ppm. The results are compared to the measurements and reference calculations in Table V. All parameter configuration lead to similar values (less than 1% for the cumulative weight), close to the measurements and to the reference calculations.

The computed power are normalized and integrated over the z-axis and then compared to TRIPOLI-5 [8] in Figure 3 for a specific core configuration with group D partially inserted. The parameter sets are given per core quarter, and the pin-by-pin relative differences in %. The root mean squared error (RMSE) between APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR and TRIPOLI-5 normalized power is also given in Figure 3.

Table V. Computed bank worths (pcm) for different parameter sets using APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR and from benchmark's reference measurements and reference calculations.

Param. set	Rod bank	A	B	C	D	SA	SB	SC	SD	Total
	a (FA)		910.7	912.7	1027.1	1411.3	432.9	1118.6	464.7	
b		913.7	862.8	1011.6	1391.0	408.3	1081.6	447.8	448.8	6565.6
c		883.9	883.9	986.6	1373.5	437.5	1073.5	456.3	456.3	6551.4
d		885.5	886.5	989.2	1378.0	439.3	1076.1	457.1	457.1	6568.9
e		893.7	871.8	988.5	1381.4	432.5	1070.4	454.2	454.2	6546.9
f		856.0	898.8	948.6	1364.0	479.5	1052.4	468.6	468.6	6536.5
Mean (std)		891 (19)	886 (16)	992 (24)	1383 (15)	438 (21)	1079 (20)	458 (7)	458 (7)	6585 (71)
Measurements [7]		843	879	951	1342	435	1056	480	480	6467
KENO-VI [7]		898	875	984	1386	447	1066	499	499	6654

Figure 3. Comparison of axially integrated power on the core North-East quarter to TRIPOLI-5 [8].

The impact of the number of radial *traverses* used is clearly visible in Figure 3: while in the parameter set (c), with 1 effective radial *traverse*, the power near the reflectors is underestimated and is slightly overestimated in the core, the use of 4 *traverses* (parameter set (f)) leads to an opposite behavior, with an overestimation of the power near the reflectors and an underestimation of the power inside the core.

Moreover, the scattering anisotropy used for the calculation of the reflector cross-sections has a strong influence on the resulting power and reactivity, while the anisotropy order used for the core assemblies has a more limited impact. The discrepancies near the reflectors are greatly reduced from parameter set (b), using P0c anisotropy, to parameter set (c), using P3 anisotropy. The reactivity is also improved by about 55 pcm, from approximately -315 to -260 pcm. Combined with the use of 4 radial *traverses* instead of 1, the reactivity of critical cases is improved by approximately 115 pcm, from -315 to -200 pcm. The 4 *traverses* case will be further investigated and comparisons with 2D models are considered for future work.

The axial powers and Bank D worth are compared to TRIPOLI-5 [8] and KENO-VI [7] results in Figures 4 and 5. APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR results are close to the reference calculations, with errors of less than a few percent for all pin-by-pin cases. The larger discrepancies for the axial power near the bottom and the top of the core may come from different top and bottom reflector models in APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR versus TRIPOLI-5. Further inside the core, the discrepancies are limited to approximately 2%. More

Figure 4. Axial power comparison for the different parameter sets to TRIPOLI-5 [8] (black), in normalized power (left) and in relative differences (right).

Figure 5. Comparison of Bank D worth from APOLLO3[®]-SIGAR to KENO-VI [7] (black). Parameter set (a) is within 2-5% of KENO-VI; sets (b) – (f) are within -3 – +0.5%].

investigations are foreseen to improve the models.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The new generation code APOLLO3[®], with the SIGAR API, has been used to simulate the TVA WB1 core at HZP. Several lattice modeling options have been used, allowing to perform a sensitivity analysis of the different parameters on the full-core calculations. Good agreement has been found with the benchmark’s measurements and reference calculations, as well as with CEA TRIPOLI-5 simulations.

From this study, the use of P3-anisotropy for the calculation of reflector cross-sections seems to be recommended, regardless of the number of radial *traverses* used. Further investigations and comparisons with 2D models are under development. For the specific BOL conditions and configurations investigated in this paper, the use of P3-anisotropy for the assembly homogenized cross-sections does not seem to significantly improve the simulation results.

These modeling options will also be tested to take into account the evolution during TVA WB1 cycle 1 and the configurations of the following cycles.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors thank APOLLO3[®] and SIGAR development teams. The authors would like to express their appreciation to the benchmark team and individually to Dr. P. Rouxelin and Distinguished Professor Dr. K. Ivanov. APOLLO3[®] is a registered trademark of CEA. The authors gratefully acknowledge Electricité de France (EDF) and Framatome for their long-term partnership and their support.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Mosca et al. "APOLLO3®: Overview of the New Code Capabilities for Reactor Physics Analysis." *NSE*, **volume 199**(sup1), p. 3 (2025).
- [2] D. Mancusi et al. "Overview of TRIPOLI-5, a Monte Carlo code for HPC." *EPJ Nuclear Sci & Tech*, **volume 10**, p. 26 (2024). Publisher: EDP Sciences.
- [3] "Deterministic Safety Analysis for Nuclear Power Plants." Technical Report No. SSG-2 (Rev. 1), IAEA, Vienna (2019).
- [4] Vaglio-Gaudard et al. "Overview of multiphysics R&D activities at the CEA/IRESNE institute." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 192**, p. 109957 (2023).
- [5] T. Albagami et al. "TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Multi-Physics MultiCycle Depletion Benchmark - Specifications and Support Data - v2.3.5." Technical Report NEA/EGMPEBV/DOC(2025), NEA (2025).
- [6] N. G. Castaing et al. "SIGAR: an APOLLO3®-based framework for PWR analysis." In *M&C 2025*, pp. 356–365. Denver, CO (2025).
- [7] A. T. Godfrey. "VERA Core Physics Benchmark Progression Problem Specifications." Technical Report Revision 4, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (2014).
- [8] B. Vezzoni et al. "OECD/NEA TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Benchmark: Overview of R&D and Industrial French solutions." *NSE* (submitted).
- [9] M. Livolant and F. Jeanpierre. "Autoprotection des Résonances dans les Réacteurs Nucléaires. Application aux Isotopes Lourds." Note Technique CEA-R-4533, CEA, Gif-sur-Yvette (1974).
- [10] A. Brighenti et al. "New Thermal and Leakage Synthetic Algorithms Applied to Best Estimate Schemes in Lattice Calculations." pp. 2164–2173 (2024).
- [11] A.-M. Baudron and J.-J. Lautard. "MINOS: A Simplified P_n Solver for Core Calculation." *NSE*, **volume 155**(2), pp. 250–263 (2007).